

Table 1. Infectivity of GLH on TN1 seedlings exposed for 1 d to caged or uncaged RTV-infected stubble of IR64 and TN1 2 wk after harvest. IRRI, 1987.

Cultivar	Caged stubble ^a					Uncaged stubble ^b				
	GLH introduced (no.)	GLH recovered and tested (no.)	Disease transmission (%)			GLH introduced (no.)	GLH recovered and tested (no.)	Disease transmission (%)		
			RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV			RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
IR64	1600	389	25	22	4	800	12	17	33	0
TN1	800	395	28	33	2	400	31	45	23	0

^aIR64 (80 stubbles) and TN1 (40) exposed to 20 GLH/stubble. ^bIR64 (40) and TN1 (20) exposed to 20 GLH/stubble.

RTBV and RTSV, IR26 infected with RTBV alone, and IR54 infected with RTSV alone were used. (Infection was confirmed by ELISA.)

The stubbles were potted individually and covered with mylar cages. Virus-free green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* were introduced for a 4-d acquisition feeding, then released individually on TN1 seedlings for a 24-h inoculation feeding.

Three weeks later, inoculated seedlings were indexed by latex test. GLH that had fed on doubly infected IR22 stubble transmitted 60% RTBV + RTSV, 17% RTBV, and 14% RTSV. GLH fed on doubly infected IR36 stubble transmitted 25% RTBV + RTSV, 28% RTBV, and 7% RTSV. GLH fed on RTSV-infected IR54 stubble transmitted 8% RTSV. No transmission was obtained on RTBV-

Table 2. Infectivity of GLH field population collected on 1- and 4-wk-old IR64 and TN1 stubbles. IRRI, 1987.

Cultivar	From 1-wk-old stubble					From 4-wk-old stubble				
	GLH density (no./10 sweeps)	Total GLH tested (no.)	TN1 infected (%)			GLH density (no./10 sweeps)	Total GLH tested (no.)	TN1 infected (%)		
			B+S	B	S			B+S	B	S
IR64	4	11	0	0	0	9	45	0	0	0
TN1	31	31	0	7	0	14	41	1	3	0

infected IR26 stubble.

In a field study, caged and uncaged stubbles of IR64 and TN1 naturally infected with both RTBV and RTSV were used as virus sources 2 wk after harvest. Virus-free male GLH were introduced onto the stubbles, recovered the following day, and tested for infectivity. Field GLH populations collected by sweep net on 1- and 4-wk-

old stubbles also were tested for infectivity.

Although GLH mortality was higher on IR64 stubble than on TN1 stubble, infectivity of the vectors did not differ significantly (Table 1). Field population collected on 1- and 4-wk-old TN1 stubbles had low levels of infectivity; those collected on IR64 stubbles were not infective (Table 2). □

Effect of potassium level on bacterial blight (BB) incidence and rice yield

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IR20 seedlings were raised in concrete pots during navarai (Feb-May) 1988. K was applied at different levels (0, 21, 42, 62, and 83 kg/ha). N and P were applied uniformly, at 100 and 50 kg/ha, respectively.

At 60 d, seedlings were clip-inoculated with BB *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* suspension at 10⁶ cells/ml. Distilled water was used for control.

Effect of K application and *X. c. pv. oryzae* inoculation on BB incidence and grain and straw yields of IR20. Tamil Nadu, India, 1988.

K (kg/ha)	Disease incidence ^a (%)	Decrease (%) from control	Grain yield			Straw yield		
			Healthy (g/pot)	Inoculated (g/pot)	Decrease (%) due to infection	Healthy (g/pot)	Inoculated (g/pot)	Decrease (%) due to infection
0	36.7 (36.6)	—	23.7	21.4	10.6	51.3	43.9	16.9
21	27.0 (31.2)	24.2	26.4	24.6	7.1	55.4	49.1	12.8
42	25.8 (30.5)	27.6	30.1	28.9	4.3	58.2	53.1	9.4
62	23.5 (28.9)	34.2	32.3	31.6	2.2	63.6	60.2	5.6
83	21.2 (27.4)	40.6	33.2	32.7	1.5	65.2	62.9	3.7
			LSD (P = 0.05) 1.8			LSD (P = 0.05) 1.8		

^a Mean of 3 replications. Angular transformed values are in parentheses.

Plants were scored for disease incidence 14 d after inoculation. Disease incidence decreased with increasing K (see table).

Grain and straw yields of both

healthy and inoculated plants increased with K application, but BB inoculation caused a significant yield difference. That difference lessened with increased K. □